

Transition to Organic Farming in Italy through a Dynamic Mathematical Programming Model: Impacts on Agricultural Area and Budget Allocations

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Introduction

One of the main objectives of the European Commission's Farm to Fork (F2F) Strategy is to increase the share of agricultural land under organic farming to 25%. However, achieving this goal depends on several factors. Organic farming differs from conventional farming in several aspects, including management practices, productivity, and risk exposure (Baker et al., 2020; Bonfiglio and Arzeni, 2019). Moreover, the conversion phase is particularly challenging since while higher prices are expected to offset lower yields, this is not always the case (Acs et al., 2009; Buttinelli et al., 2021; Hanson et al., 2004), especially for livestock and vegetable products (Seufert et al., 2012). Many studies model organic conversion, typically assuming full conversion and focusing on representative farms (Acs et al., 2009; Kerselaers et al., 2007; Smith et al., 2018) or considering the organic target of 25% jointly with other F2F objectives (Barreiro-Hurle et al., 2021; Henning et al., 2021). Recently, Kremmydas et al. (2024) and Kremmydas et al. (2023) used a static farm-level model to study the conversion to organic farming, assessing the underlying dynamics and examining the effects of different budget allocations on achieving the F2F target of 25%.

This study contributes to the literature by adopting a dynamic approach that simulates farm-level decisions, explicitly distinguishing between the conversion and maintenance phases, and analyzing scenarios where organic farming expansion is incentivized by larger budgets. The objective is to estimate the financial support required to meet these targets, assuming that higher budgets encourage conversion. The study employs AGRITALIM, an agro-supply economic model based on microeconomic data, able to provide results at the farm-level (Cortignani et al., 2022). AGRITALIM is a non-linear mathematical programming model combining Leontief technology for variable costs with a quadratic cost function, calibrated using the Positive Mathematical Programming (PMP) approach (Howitt, 1995; Paris and Arfini, 1995). The objective function maximizes farm operating income, incorporating market prices, production functions, agricultural policies, and depreciation costs. Constraints include land, labor, water, and feed availability. The voluntary conversion choice, modeled with a binary variable, depends on several factors, such as CAP payments and yield and cost

differences between conventional and organic farming. The underlying key assumption is that achieving the 25% target at the national level, in line with F2F goals, requires regional contributions based on past trends and opportunities in organic farming expansion. Currently, the model was applied to a sample of 378 conventional farms in Lazio for the year 2020 using Italian Farm Accountancy Data Network (FADN) data. Simulations estimate the budget needed to achieve organic area increases of 5%, 8%, and 12% in this region, assuming that the positive trend observed in recent years will continue to drive organic expansion. Preliminary results suggest that the response to conversion is rigid, with only modest increases in organic adoption even with higher budget allocations.

The strength of our approach lies in AGRITALIM's ability to capture farm-level decision-making and account for cost and productivity variations across the conversion and maintenance stages. Using observed farm-level data guarantees a more accurate representation of farms' responses to policy and market conditions while allowing for the simulation of multiple scenarios. Future steps may involve extending the application to other regions and integrating econometric techniques to estimate price premiums and cost variations, further improving the model's ability to realistically capture farms' choices in transitioning to organic farming.

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